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The Copenhagen Symposium

on Human-Centered
Software Engineering AI

FINAL REPORT

2023

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The Copenhagen Symposium

on Human-Centered
Software Engineering AI

PART

1

SUMMARY

The Copenhagen Symposium on Human-Centered Software Engineering AI was an event dedicated to discuss the implications of integrating Large Language Models and generative AI into software engineering.

Central to the symposium were discussions on the transformation of Software Engineering (SE) roles in the AI era, transitioning from traditional tasks to orchestrating and managing AI tools.

A significant emphasis was placed on the ethical dimensions of AI, with a call for transparency, accountability, and adherence to ethical standards in AI systems.

The symposium also explored the dynamic impact of AI on team structures, Agile processes and workflows, highlighting the necessity of redefining team dynamics in light of AI integration.

The discussions converged on the importance of adapting to the rapid advancements in AI, advocating for a flexible and proactive approach to the integration of AI in SE.

The symposium concluded with a forward-looking perspective, envisioning a future in SE that synergizes human ingenuity with AI capabilities.

TRANSFORMATION OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING ROLES

This section synthesizes the outcomes of a symposium focusing on the evolving paradigms in software engineering in light of the advent of Large Language Models (LLMs).

The emergent AI-driven shift posits a reconfigured ecosystem where conventional software engineering roles are augmented or replaced by advanced AI functionalities.

Code Artisans to System Architects

The symposium underscored a paradigmatic shift from software engineers as code artisans to system architects. This evolution repositions the engineer from a constructor of discrete code blocks to an architect of complex, AI-integrated systems. The system architect role necessitates a comprehensive understanding of AI mechanisms and a visionary approach to integrating these into transformative solutions.

Enhanced Multimodal Interfacing

Corresponding to the role transformation, there was a consensus on the need for software engineers to engage with AI through an extended spectrum of interfaces. This includes, but is not limited to, traditional programming languages, encompassing the use of visual aids, mockups, and sketches. Such multimodal communication facilitates an intricate dialogue with AI systems, leveraging the AI's capacity for processing diverse data formats to enhance the intuitiveness and robustness of the development process.

AI Contingency Analysts

The symposium discussions introduced the necessity for 'AI Contingency Analysts. Tasked with navigating the multifaceted nature of AI, these specialists focus on crisis management and the proactive identification of potential system failures. Their role is critical in ensuring AI operations remain within ethical boundaries and predefined performance parameters, applying human judgment to counteract AI unpredictability.

Complexity Navigation in AI-Limited Scenarios

AI's non-omnipotent nature was a focal discussion point, highlighting the indispensable role of human intervention in scenarios that exceed AI's programmed capabilities. AI Contingency Analysts are instrumental in these situations, applying critical thinking and inventive problem-solving to bridge the gaps in AI's problem-resolution abilities.

AI Capability Conductors

The symposium posited a reimagined role for software engineers as 'AI Capability Conductors.' This role encapsulates the strategic integration and oversight of diverse AI functionalities into coherent systems. Conductors must discern the strengths and limitations of each AI module, orchestrating them to produce the optimal output — a harmonious integration akin to a symphonic composition in the realm of software solutions.

TRANSFORMATIONS

The symposium's discourse on the transformation of software engineering roles forecasts a shift towards a more synergistic, strategic, and inventive deployment of AI in software development.

It anticipates a future where software engineers will augment their competencies to exploit AI's potential fully, fostering a symbiotic relationship that bolsters both the development and sustenance of software systems.

This future mandates that software engineers not only adapt to but also guide the course of AI's role in software development, ensuring the judicious and potent application of AI tools to surmount evolving industry challenges.

TRUST AND ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS IN AI INTEGRATION

This section provides an analytical examination of trust and ethical dimensions associated with the integration of AI into software engineering, specifically focusing on the complexities introduced by advanced AI technologies such as Large Language Models.

The Facets of Trust in AI Ecosystems

The symposium delineated trust as a multi-dimensional construct pivotal to the AI integration in software engineering. It highlighted the dual nature of trust where stakeholders must place confidence not only in the AI's technical efficiency but also in the integrity of its developmental and operational processes. This encompasses the AI's task execution reliability and its predictability in behavioral patterns.

Decision-Making Transparency

The criticality of decision-making transparency in AI systems was emphasized, advocating for the necessity of these systems to elucidate their decision rationales. The symposium pointed to the imperative for AI to demonstrate the logic and data underpinning its decisions, a practice vital for the verification of AI operations by users, developers, and stakeholders, and crucial for course corrections when necessary.

Bias Recognition and Addressal

The symposium dedicated substantial attention to the recognition and mitigation of inherent biases within AI systems. These biases, stemming from the AI's training data and architectural design, potentially influence the system's functionality and decision-making processes. Surmounting these biases is not solely a technical hurdle but an ethical obligation to prevent the perpetuation or intensification of societal disparities.

Ethical Commitments and Developer Duties

The symposium explored the ethical responsibilities incumbent upon developers in the age of AI, accentuating their role in ensuring AI systems' adherence to ethical norms. This duty extends to proactive management of AI's societal impacts, including the obsolescence of certain job functions and the broader socioeconomic repercussions.

Call for Regulatory Frameworks

There was a unified agreement on the necessity for robust regulatory frameworks and standards to undergird ethical AI deployment. These frameworks are envisaged to guide responsible AI development, deter misuse, and formalize accountability measures. The symposium advocated for anticipatory policymaking to preemptively address emergent challenges and establish ethical AI integration trajectories.

Standards as Ethical Benchmarks

The symposium identified the establishment of rigorous and universally endorsed standards as essential for steering AI within SE. Such standards should encapsulate both the technical and ethical tenets, aligning AI initiatives with societal values and fostering public trust through a commitment to the common good and societal welfare.

2 S I O N S C O N C L U S I O N S

In summation, the symposium's discourse on trust and ethics in AI outlined the intricate challenges and obligations before the SE community in this transformative era.

Trust in AI systems is to be seen as a dynamic accreditation, sustained by steadfast, transparent, and equitable AI practices.

The call for comprehensive ethical frameworks and standards was a recurrent theme, underscoring the community's dedication to ethical navigation and the principled application of AI, ensuring its contribution to societal advancement and adherence to values of fairness and justice.

AI AND TEAM DYNAMICS IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

This section discusses the implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly Large Language Models, on team dynamics within software engineering contexts, articulating how AI integration reshapes collaboration and team functionality.

Incorporation of LLMs in Team Environments

Discussions at the symposium centralized on the integration of LLMs as quasi-team members within software development groups. LLMs are postulated to function not solely as auxiliary tools but as quasi-collaborators, contributing to both the generative and analytical dimensions of software projects. This integration challenges traditional notions of team composition and necessitates novel project management methodologies.

Optimization of Team Dynamics

The capacity of LLMs to augment team dynamics and operational efficiency was acknowledged. It was proposed that LLMs could assume responsibility for tasks that are algorithmically repetitive, liberating human colleagues for work necessitating innovation and critical evaluation. This reallocation has the potential to optimize the deployment of human intellectual capital and elevate overall team productivity. Further, the inclusion of LLMs might engender a more egalitarian working environment by compensating for disparities in team skill levels and introducing varied computational problem-solving perspectives.

The Emergence of Prompt Engineering

'Prompt Engineering' was identified as a pivotal communicative conduit for interfacing with AI. The proficiency in constructing queries that elicit pertinent and applicable responses from AI is becoming increasingly vital as LLMs evolve. Symposium exchanges posited that prompt engineering may emerge as a distinct specialization within software engineering teams, central to leveraging LLM capabilities fully.

AI-Enhanced Collaborative Processes

The symposium explored the transformation of collaborative paradigms via AI integration, with a focus on activities like pair programming. In such scenarios, an LLM could hypothetically act as one participant, offering code suggestions, issue detection, and real-time solution generation. AI's role in decision-making matrices was also scrutinized, contemplating its potential to influence determinations throughout the software development lifecycle.

Reconfiguring Team Architectures

The potential necessity to reconceptualize traditional team frameworks in the wake of LLM integration was examined. As LLMs assume progressively complex functions, a convergence of developer roles and AI proficiencies is anticipated, prompting the emergence of novel team dynamics and role delineations. This evolution demands a strategic reconsideration of team configuration to ensure seamless AI incorporation and clarity in role assignments.

3 S Y M P O S I U M C O N C L U S I O N S

The symposium's deliberations on AI and team dynamics in software engineering portrayed a future where LLMs are intricately interwoven into team structures, acting as a fulcrum for enhanced efficiency and a catalyst for structural evolution.

It was recognized that while this integration introduces complexities, it also holds the promise of substantial improvements in the software development paradigm.

Mastery in AI communication, particularly through prompt engineering, is projected to be crucial for capitalizing on the potential of AI within team-based software engineering endeavors.

AWARENESS, EDUCATION, AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT IN AI

The symposium addressed the imperative of cultivating awareness and education regarding Large Language Models within software engineering, emphasizing the expansion of these efforts to diverse stakeholders.

Expansion of AI Educational Outreach

The dialogues underscored the necessity of broadening AI education beyond the software industry's ecosystem. It was proposed that this educational expansion encompass interdisciplinary domains, involving not just technologists but also domain experts, educators, policymakers, and the public at large. Such broad-based knowledge dissemination is key to fostering a holistic understanding of AI's multidimensional impact.

Comprehension of LLM Scope and Limitations

A deep comprehension of LLMs' capacities and limitations was marked as essential. Discussions revolved around the transformative potential of LLMs while also emphasizing the significance of recognizing their operational boundaries, ethical implications, and the contextually appropriate application domains.

Ethical Paradigms in AI Utilization

Ethical considerations in AI usage formed a core theme. There was a unified stance on the necessity for crafting and adopting ethical frameworks to guide LLM development and utilization. This includes confronting challenges such as biases, data privacy, and the prevention of misuse. It was posited that these ethical precepts should be integral to AI educational content, cultivating a responsible ethos amongst emergent developers and users.

Community Involvement and Knowledge Dissemination

The symposium advocated for robust community engagement and the creation of knowledge-sharing infrastructures. Collaborative initiatives among academia, the tech sector, policymakers, and end-user groups are vital for a transparent and iterative learning process regarding AI's societal repercussions.

Standardization of AI Terminology

Standardizing terminology in AI discourse was recognized as crucial for clarity and precision in communication. The symposium highlighted that public misunderstandings often arise from the use of ambiguous or inaccurate AI-related terms, affecting public perception and policy formulation. Educational resources, public discussions, and policy dialogues should consistently apply accurate terminology to ensure informed and responsible discourse about AI.

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In summary, the symposium's emphasis on awareness, education, and community interaction calls for a collective approach to inform the trajectory of AI development.

By extending educational outreach, instilling ethical guidelines, and promoting active community participation, the groundwork is laid for AI to evolve in a manner that is responsible, ethical, and advantageous across diverse spheres of influence.

ADAPTING TO AI-INDUCED CHANGES IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

The symposium provided a detailed analysis of the software engineering community's adaptation to the AI revolution, with a specific emphasis on the integration of Large Language Models.

The Adaptation Process

The symposium narratives drew an analogy between the software engineering community's reaction to AI progressions and the psychological stages of grief, illuminating the emotional and intellectual journey of adaptation.

This journey is characterized by initial resistance, followed by a period of acclimatization, and culminating in an optimistic embrace of new possibilities enabled by AI.

AI as an Augmentation Instrument

Discussions at the symposium focused on the acceptance of AI as an augmentation tool within the software engineering repertoire. This conceptual shift from AI as a disruptor to an enhancer is pivotal, underscoring AI's role in extending, not supplanting, human expertise.

Redefinition of Human-AI Synergy

A significant point of discussion was the need to reconceptualize the human-AI dynamic within software development. Envisioned as a synergistic partnership, this new paradigm positions AI as an augmentative force to human intelligence, where each complements the other's strengths.

AI as a Catalyst for Human Skill Enhancement

The symposium deliberated on AI's role in elevating human capabilities. It was proposed that AI's capacity to automate routine tasks could free human engineers to address more intricate and inventive aspects of software development, fostering a more innovative and productive engineering process.

Preservation and Evolution of Human Skills

It was emphasized that in an AI-centric future, the pertinence of human-centric skills like ethical discernment, critical analysis, and innovation becomes more pronounced. These skills are integral to ensuring that AI deployment remains congruent with ethical norms and societal values.

5 S N O S U C N C O

In summary, the symposium articulated that adaptation to AI in software engineering is a multifaceted and continuous process, encompassing technological proficiency as well as a reimagining of human engineers' roles.

The collective vision is one of AI as a collaborative ally, amplifying human expertise, creativity, and ethical oversight, thereby enriching the field of software engineering.

SUMMARY OF THE SYMPOSIUM'S DISCUSSIONS

The symposium offered a forward-thinking analysis on the transformation within software engineering, catalyzed by human-centric AI technologies. It concentrated on the redefinition of roles precipitated by the integration of AI, with a special focus on the implications of Large Language Models.

Transformation of SE Roles

The symposium identified a significant evolution in SE roles. It emphasized the transition from traditional programming to managing AI capabilities, positioning software engineers as architects of an AI-augmented development process. This transformation underscores the need for a balance between technical acumen, strategic management, and ethical stewardship in SE.

Centrality of Trust and Ethical Frameworks

Discussions on trust and ethics were prominent, advocating for the need for transparent, reliable, and verifiable AI systems. The symposium stressed the multidimensional nature of trust and the imperative to confront biases and ethical challenges in AI. The establishment of comprehensive regulatory standards was urged to facilitate ethical AI practices in line with societal expectations.

AI's Influence on Team Dynamics

The symposium also explored AI's influence on SE team dynamics. LLMs' potential as collaborators in enhancing team efficacy and inclusivity was examined. The importance of effective communication, notably through 'Prompt Engineering,' was accentuated, as was AI's role in redefining collaborative and decision-making processes.

Importance of AI Education and Public Discourse

The necessity for expansive AI education and public awareness was a key point. The symposium advocated for educational initiatives to prepare various stakeholders for the AI transition, emphasizing community engagement and the sharing of knowledge as pillars for a well-informed public discourse on AI.

Navigating AI-Induced Transformations

The discussions concluded on the note of adaptation by the SE community to the disruptive impact of AI. This encompasses a re-evaluation of the human-AI interface and the utilization of AI to amplify human skills. The value placed on human intuition, innovation, and ethical judgment was deemed essential for navigating the AI-augmented future of SE.

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The symposium synthesized a vision for software engineering's future, integrating AI advancements with a commitment to ethical and human-centric values. This integrated perspective anticipates a synergistic human-AI alliance, with innovation and ethical responsibility as the fundamental tenets of a progressive SE domain.

Moving from these broad discussions to a detailed analysis, the following section will delve into specific research inquiries that emerged from the symposium. These questions are intended to steer the software engineering community toward an ethically aware, AI-integrated future.

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PART

2

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In this section, we explore the key research questions raised during the symposium. The focus is on understanding the role of generative AI in automating tasks within software engineering, distinguishing the ethical use of AI in research, and assessing the reliability of AI-generated outputs. These questions are essential in shaping how AI is integrated into software engineering, ensuring it is used responsibly and effectively. The discussions here aim to provide a clear and practical perspective on navigating the challenges and opportunities of AI in the field, offering insights into how AI is transforming software engineering today and in the future.

ASSESSING THE ADOPTION OF GENERATIVE AI ON SOFTWARE ENGINEERING PRACTICES

The integration and adoption of generative AI into software engineering practices has emerged as a pivotal theme in the symposium, prompting robust discussions about its potential to redefine the industry's landscape.

Research Questions:

- How does generative AI affect estimation, prioritization, and test prioritization?
- How will generative AI disrupt team creativity?
- Exploring the long-term (longitudinal) effects across different units of analysis:

A) Individual Level:

- How professionals perceive their productivity in conjunction with AI tools.
- The level of trust individuals place in the decisions made by generative AI systems.
- The degree of confidence individuals have in their ability to leverage AI in their roles effectively

B) Team Level:

- The changes in collaborative workflows and communication as teams integrate AI into their daily operations.
- The adaptations necessary for onboarding new team members into an AI-enhanced work environment.

C) Organizational Level:

- The depth of generative AI integration within companies, assessed through the Human-AI Collaboration and Adaptation Framework (HACAF)¹, which considers various dimensions such as strategy, culture, and employee engagement.

¹ D. Russo. Navigating the Complexity of Generative AI Adoption in Software Engineering. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology*, In Press, 49 pp. 2024.

Generative AI in Estimation, Prioritization, and Testing

A primary line of inquiry examines the repercussions of generative AI on the bedrock processes of project management. Questions revolve around AI's ability to refine estimation accuracy through advanced data analytics and its potential to overhaul prioritization frameworks. The role of AI in test suite optimization is scrutinized, with an eye on how it may revolutionize the identification of key testing domains, enhancing the efficacy of quality assurance methodologies.

Generative AI and Team Creativity

The symposium also explored the intersection of generative AI and team creativity. The research questions here address whether AI's integration will supplant traditional creative workflows or engender novel avenues for ideation. Investigations will consider AI's collaborative role in creative processes, its influence on ideation sessions, and its overall impact on the creative cadence within team settings. This includes a critical look at how teams might need to adapt their creative strategies to leverage AI's capabilities fully.

Exploring the Long-Term Effects Across Units of Analysis

The investigation focuses into the pervasive influence of generative AI across individual, team, and organizational tiers within software engineering. At the individual level, it measures perceptions of productivity when working alongside AI, the trust in AI's decision-making, and the self-efficacy in using AI technologies. For teams, it examines the evolution of collaboration and communication dynamics in light of AI integration and the onboarding processes for newcomers in such transformed settings. On an organizational scale, the survey employs the HACAF model to gauge the extent of AI adoption, scrutinizing the interplay between AI implementation and various organizational dimensions, including strategy formulation, cultural alignment, and the engagement of personnel. This multifaceted approach aims to capture the comprehensive impact of generative AI, considering different angles of the research phenomena.

7 SYMPOSIUM DISCUSSIONS

The symposium set the stage for a comprehensive investigation into the transformative effects of generative AI on software engineering. It established a foundational understanding of the critical need for research that explores the recalibration of project management practices, the evolution of creative dynamics in teams, and the longitudinal effects of AI across the spectrum of the SE landscape. Emphasizing a need for adaptive strategies, the discussions pointed toward the importance of understanding AI's multifaceted impact at all levels of the engineering hierarchy, ensuring that generative AI is harnessed to augment human expertise and innovation in the realm of software engineering.

AUTOMATION AND ETHICAL USE OF AI IN SE

The symposium brought forth an array of thought-provoking inquiries related to the automation capabilities of generative AI in software engineering and the ethical considerations inherent to its deployment.

Research Questions:

- Which software engineering tasks can/should be automated using generative AI?
- How can we distinguish acceptable vs. unacceptable uses of Generative AI in research/science?
- How does generative AI redefine reliability and its assessment?

Identifying Opportunities for Automation

A key inquiry concerns identifying which SE tasks are candidates for AI-driven automation. The investigation here seeks to delineate the boundaries of AI efficacy, ensuring automation serves to enhance, not erode, the quality and creativity inherent in human-led engineering. Researchers must establish criteria that balance efficiency gains with the retention of essential human oversight, such as heuristic problem-solving and innovation.

Navigating Ethical Boundaries

The symposium emphasized the need for a clear ethical framework that delineates the boundaries of AI application in SE research. This ethical inquiry is two-fold: it must consider the direct implications for the integrity of research outcomes and address broader societal impacts. Developing guidelines for ethical AI use necessitates a multi-disciplinary approach, drawing from ethics, law, and SE practices to create standards that prevent misuse and abuse while fostering beneficial innovation.

Reconceptualizing Reliability

The conventional understanding of reliability in software systems is challenged by the opaque and complex nature of AI outputs. The symposium's discourse suggests that new evaluative frameworks are needed, ones that account for the probabilistic reasoning of AI and the potential for biases in training data.

These frameworks must not only provide metrics for reliability but also offer transparency to facilitate trust and understanding among stakeholders.

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Incorporating these research questions emphasizes the need for a strategic approach to AI integration in SE—one that optimizes the capabilities of AI for task automation while maintaining ethical integrity and redefining reliability. The symposium advocates for ongoing evaluation and adaptation within the SE community, ensuring that AI applications support and extend human expertise rather than supplant it. The future of SE, as discussed, will likely see AI as a collaborator that enhances the unique human aspects of the engineering process.

RELIABILITY AND PROCESS EVOLUTION

At the symposium, the discourse on reliability and process evolution in the context of generative AI in software engineering was both rigorous and expansive. Key questions emerged on how the advent of AI is redefining traditional SE paradigms.

Research Questions:

- How does generative AI redefine reliability and its assessment?
- Does generative AI shift the core evolutionary artifact from the codebase to the test suite?
- How does generative AI affect estimation, prioritization, and test prioritization?

Re-assessing Reliability

The symposium postulated that the reliability of AI-generated code necessitates a re-assessment of what we consider reliable in the first place. Research in this area must explore new validation paradigms that go beyond current code review and testing standards. This means not just identifying potential failures but understanding the decision-making process of AI, its failure modes, and how they differ from human-derived errors.

Evolving Developmental Focus

As generative AI potentially shifts the core of development from the codebase to the test suite, research must explore how this transition will alter the software development lifecycle. This includes examining the role of AI in continuous integration and deployment pipelines, and how it may change the prioritization of testing and quality assurance tasks.

Impact on Project Management

Generative AI's influence on project management presents a research opportunity. AI's potential to provide more accurate estimates, to identify critical path tasks, and to optimize resource allocation necessitates a fresh look at project management methodologies. Research should seek to quantify the benefits and identify the challenges posed by AI in this context, ensuring that project outcomes are not compromised by over-reliance on AI-driven estimations.

9 S N O S U L C N C

This exploration of research questions underscores the multifaceted nature of AI's impact on SE. As AI reshapes the landscape of SE, research must be both responsive and anticipatory, developing new frameworks and methodologies that address the unique characteristics and challenges of AI. The insights gained from the symposium point toward a future where software engineering becomes more adaptive, innovative, and synergistic with AI, fostering an environment where human intellect and machine intelligence co-evolve.

VALIDATION, TRUST, AND TEAM DYNAMICS

The symposium provided a comprehensive exploration into the effects of Large Language Models on critical areas of software engineering such as validation, trust, and team dynamics. These discussions, enriched by specific research questions, deep into how LLMs are reshaping these fundamental aspects of SE.

Research Questions:

How does LLM impact:

- Validation?
- Trust?
- Productivity?
- Team-work?
- Ownership?

Implications of LLMs on Validation

The symposium placed a spotlight on the effects of LLMs on software validation. Questions were raised about LLMs' potential to refine validation techniques, ensuring that software complies with specified criteria and meets end-user demands effectively. The discussion considered whether LLMs could increase the precision of validation processes or introduce new variables that developers need to manage.

Building Trust in AI-Enabled Systems

Trust in systems empowered by AI, specifically LLMs, emerged as a critical inquiry. The symposium dissected the factors contributing to the trustworthiness of these systems, pondering the reliability and integrity of LLM outputs. The dialogue tackled the challenge of designing LLMs that are not only technically proficient but also align with ethical standards and societal norms, thus fostering user trust, especially in high-stakes scenarios.

Enhancing Productivity with LLMs

LLMs' capacity to boost productivity in software development was scrutinized. The symposium assessed the likelihood of LLMs accelerating development timelines, optimizing workflows, and augmenting team efficiency. This included evaluating LLMs' capability in automating mundane tasks, thus freeing developers to concentrate on more intricate and innovative development aspects.

Transforming Team Dynamics with LLMs

The potential transformation in team dynamics precipitated by LLMs was a significant area of exploration. The symposium aimed to elucidate how LLMs could act as catalysts for enhanced collaboration or disrupt existing team structures. It delved into the prospects of LLMs serving as adjuncts to human skill and creativity and the ramifications of their integration on conventional team operations.

Ownership Challenges in the AI Era

The symposium also tackled the complex issue of ownership in AI-assisted software development. Discussions sought to unravel how the employment of LLMs impacts the delineation and management of intellectual property, contemplating the intricacies of attributing contributions to software co-created with AI systems.

10 S N O S U L C N C C

In conclusion, the symposium's in-depth discussions on validation, trust, and team dynamics articulated the extensive and intricate impact of LLMs on software engineering. The conversations revealed the necessity for an understanding of LLM capabilities and challenges, their ethical adoption in SE practices, and their influence on fostering a collaborative and productive development environment. These insights collectively highlight the need for software engineering to evolve its methodologies, frameworks, and policies to accommodate the disruptive nature of LLM technologies.

DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

The symposium focused into the evolving role of Large Language Models in the fields of design and software architecture within software engineering, prompting a series of insightful questions about their impact and utility.

Research Questions:

- How does LLM impact design and architecture-level code quality attributes and their tradeoffs?
- How can LLM-backed tools provide design space exploration support?

Influence of LLMs on Design and Architecture

The symposium's conversations delved into how LLMs might influence key quality attributes of software architecture, such as modularity, reusability, performance, security, and scalability. The discussions aimed to unpack the extent to which LLMs understand and can potentially optimize these attributes while acknowledging the inherent trade-offs. Questions centered on LLMs' capacity to automate the enhancement of these quality attributes and the potential for shifting priority among them based on context-specific requirements.

Managing Trade-Offs in Code Quality

Exploring the management of trade-offs in code quality attributes through LLMs was highlighted as a research priority. While LLMs may bring advancements in certain quality attributes, they may also impose constraints on others. The need to develop technical strategies for balancing these trade-offs emerged as a crucial point of investigation. This involves creating methodologies for quantifying the impact of LLM interventions and determining how to mitigate any negative effects on the software quality spectrum.

LLM-Backed Design Space Exploration

The symposium also explored the role of LLMs in providing support for design space exploration. This includes examining how LLM-backed tools can aid architects in navigating the vast array of design options, evaluating potential architectural patterns, and understanding the long-term implications of these decisions. The discussion aimed to identify the potential for LLMs to provide predictive insights into architectural decisions and their downstream effects on system performance and maintenance.

Navigating Complex Architectural Decisions

Participants discussed the prospect of employing LLMs to navigate complex software architecture decisions. The potential for LLMs to contribute to decision-making processes by offering data-driven insights and predicting outcomes based on historical trends and patterns was a focal point. Research in this area seeks to understand how LLMs can augment the expertise of software architects and facilitate the adoption of more sophisticated, context-aware architectural solutions.

FINAL SYMPOSIUM RESULTS CONCLUSIONS

The symposium's discussions provided a comprehensive view of the transformative role LLMs could play in software design and architecture. The potential for LLMs to influence the quality attributes of software, manage trade-offs, and support complex architectural decision-making processes was recognized as an area for research. These insights call for an ongoing technical exploration of LLM capabilities, aiming to develop robust tools and methodologies that optimize the strengths of LLMs and mitigate their limitations. The symposium set a direction for future work in software engineering, where innovative design and architecture practices are informed and enhanced by the integration of advanced AI technologies like LLMs.

THEORETICAL DEVELOPMENT AND INTERFACE INNOVATION

The symposium's exploration into theoretical development and interface innovation in software engineering, particularly in the context of Large Language Models, highlighted a growing trend towards abstract conceptualization and the need for novel interfaces. This shift reflects the evolving nature of SE in the age of AI.

Research Questions:

- How do we develop theories without writing code?
- How to go beyond the chat box/IDE as UI?
- Prompt Investigation & Prompt Improvement
- How do you even identify hallucinations in large generative code?

Developing Theories Beyond Traditional Programming

A central query addressed the formulation of SE theories that transcend traditional programming activities. The symposium prompted discussions on how AI could inform the creation of such theories, suggesting a trend where the theoretical underpinnings of SE are abstracted from direct code writing and are instead rooted in AI-assisted algorithmic and conceptual design. This demands a methodological innovation that can accommodate the AI-augmented landscape and guide LLM application across various SE scenarios.

Innovating Interface Designs

The symposium discussed the opportunity of interface designs that extend beyond the traditional chat box and IDE paradigms. This exploration acknowledged the necessity for interfaces that enable more profound interactions with AI, incorporating dynamic, visual, and context-aware elements to engage with LLMs more intuitively. The discussion anticipated interface innovations that cater to the complex demands of SE in the age of AI, enabling more nuanced communication and interaction with LLM systems.

Prompt Engineering and Enhancement

Prompt engineering emerged as a critical focus, considering the reliance of LLMs on high-quality prompts to produce applicable outputs. The symposium explored strategies for crafting prompts that effectively convey the context and technical requirements, thus maximizing the utility of LLM responses. This encompasses not only linguistic precision but also the incorporation of relevant technical and situational details.

Detecting AI ‘Hallucinations’

Identifying and correcting AI ‘hallucinations’—instances where LLMs generate erroneous or nonsensical code—was recognized as a significant challenge. Symposium participants delved into potential detection and rectification techniques, examining how to ensure that the code generated by LLMs adheres to expected standards of logic and functionality.

CONCLUSIONS 12

The symposium's discussions underlined a period of significant change in SE, characterized by the advancement of theoretical development and interface innovation in response to the incursion of AI and LLMs. The collective insights point towards an impending era in SE where the discipline extends beyond conventional code management to encompass strategic AI conceptualization and interaction, pushing the boundaries of current practices. As SE progresses, fostering new theoretical frameworks and pioneering user interface designs will be essential to leverage the full spectrum of AI capabilities in the engineering process.

META-COGNITIVE SKILLS AND QUALITY MEASUREMENT

The symposium brought to light the crucial need for developing meta-cognitive skills in software engineering, especially in the context of leveraging generative AI. Discussions also revolved around the assessment of software quality in the era of AI, probing the effectiveness and improvements brought about by these technologies.

Research Questions:

- What meta-cognitive skills do software engineers need to use generative AI well? How do we teach it?
- Is better software being made with generative AI? How do we measure?

Cultivating Meta-Cognitive Skills

The emphasis on meta-cognitive skills underlines a paradigm shift in the competencies required for modern software engineers. Meta-cognitive skills, such as self-awareness, reflective thinking, and adaptive learning, are increasingly important for effectively using generative AI. The symposium participants explored which specific skills are most crucial and discussed methodologies for imparting these skills to engineers and developers. The challenge lies in not only teaching technical know-how but also fostering an ability to think about the broader implications, ethical considerations, and long-term impacts of implementing AI in SE projects.

Teaching Strategies for Meta-Cognitive Skills

The discussion on teaching strategies for these skills highlighted the need for innovative educational approaches. This includes hands-on experience with AI tools, case studies that illustrate successful and problematic uses of AI, and theoretical coursework that delves into the conceptual underpinnings of AI technologies. The goal is to create a holistic learning environment that prepares SE professionals to think critically and creatively about the use of AI in their work.

Measuring Software Quality

Another significant topic was the measurement of software quality in projects that utilize generative AI. Participants questioned whether the integration of AI is indeed producing better software and, if so, how this improvement can be quantitatively and qualitatively assessed. This involves defining what 'better software' means in the context of AI – whether it refers to efficiency, reliability, user satisfaction, or innovation – and establishing metrics to evaluate these dimensions.

Developing New Metrics and Standards

The need for new metrics and standards for quality assessment in AI-enhanced software was acknowledged. As AI changes the development process, traditional metrics might no longer suffice to capture the full scope of a software's quality. Therefore, the symposium pointed towards the development of new benchmarks that consider the unique attributes and challenges of AI-generated code.

CONCLUSIONS 13

In conclusion, the symposium's discussions on meta-cognitive skills and quality measurement in SE underscore the complexity and multidimensionality of integrating AI into the field. The insights gathered highlight the necessity for SE professionals to develop skills that go beyond technical expertise, encompassing reflective thinking and ethical consideration. Simultaneously, there is a call for the industry to rethink how software quality is measured in the age of AI, ensuring that the metrics used accurately reflect the value and effectiveness of AI-integrated solutions.

FUTURE OUTLOOK, DEI, AND EMPOWERMENT OF SMALL COMPANIES

The symposium presented an insightful discourse on the future trajectory of generative AI in software engineering, its impact on diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), and the role it could play in empowering small companies. These discussions were enriched with forward-looking questions and considerations about creating an inclusive and dynamic SE landscape.

Research Questions:

- What is the 1-year, 3-year, 5-year outlook for GenAI in SE? We need fiction.
- What will the effects of GenAI on Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) in SE be?
- How do we empower small companies by recognizing the value of all kinds of software development?

Short to Medium-Term Outlook for GenAI in SE

The symposium prompted participants to contemplate the near and distant future of GenAI in SE. Questions about the 1-year, 3-year, and 5-year outlooks invited speculations and predictions, emphasizing the need for a visionary approach, potentially aided by speculative fiction, to understand and prepare for upcoming trends and transformations. This future-gazing approach is crucial for SE professionals to anticipate technological advancements and prepare for their implications within the industry.

GenAI's Impact on DEI

The effects of GenAI on DEI within the SE sector were a significant focus of discussion. Symposium participants examined how the integration of AI into SE could either contribute to or mitigate existing disparities in the field. These discussions highlighted the importance of ensuring that AI technologies are developed and utilized in ways that promote inclusivity and equal opportunity, rather than exacerbating existing inequalities. The questions raised pointed towards a conscious effort to integrate DEI considerations into the development and application of GenAI technologies.

Empowering Small Companies

Another critical topic was the empowerment of small companies in the rapidly evolving SE landscape. The discussions explored how GenAI could level the playing field by providing smaller entities with powerful tools that were previously accessible only to larger organizations. Questions were raised about recognizing and valuing diverse contributions in software development, irrespective of company size. This includes exploring ways to support small companies in harnessing GenAI for innovation, growth, and competitiveness.

Need for Inclusive and Agile Research Practices

The symposium underscored the necessity for inclusive and Agile research practices in SE. As the field continues to evolve with the advent of GenAI, there is a call for research methodologies that are adaptable, inclusive, and responsive to the fast-paced changes in technology. This approach is vital for effectively studying and understanding the multifaceted impact of AI on SE, particularly in terms of DEI and the empowerment of smaller players in the industry.

14 SYMPOSIUM RESULTS CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the symposium's exploration of the future outlook, DEI, and the empowerment of small companies in the context of GenAI in SE painted a picture of an industry on the cusp of significant change. The insights gathered from these discussions highlight the need for a forward-looking, inclusive, and adaptable approach in SE. As GenAI continues to redefine the landscape, the emphasis is on preparing for future challenges, ensuring that the benefits of AI are equitably distributed, and recognizing the diverse contributions that drive innovation and excellence in the field.

SYNTHESIZING SYMPOSIUM INSIGHTS

The symposium on human-centric AI integration in software engineering concluded with a set of complex research queries, reflecting AI's diverse impacts on the sector. These inquiries not only demand a strategic method for AI's amalgamation into SE practices but also highlight the broader, multifaceted repercussions of this technological shift.

AI's Capabilities and Multifaceted Implications

An advanced understanding of AI's capacities, particularly in the realm of generative AI and Large Language Models, was deemed imperative. This involves a comprehensive grasp that extends past algorithmic functionality to include considerations of AI's ethical, societal, and economical influences. It is critical to evaluate AI's role in advancing automation, redefining reliability standards, reshaping project management frameworks, and influencing software design paradigms.

Development of Advanced Educational Strategies

The symposium put forth the necessity for progressive educational strategies that enable SE practitioners to proficiently harness AI tools. This requires cultivating meta-cognitive abilities, a nuanced understanding of AI ethics, and an enduring commitment to learning and adaptability. The symposium recognized the dynamic nature of SE roles, calling for an educational infrastructure capable of evolving in tandem with AI's rapid development.

AI's Transformational Impact on Team Dynamics

The effect of AI on SE team dynamics was thoroughly examined. The symposium delved into how AI, especially LLMs, can be harnessed to elevate team efficiency, Agility, inclusivity, and innovation. However, integrating AI within teams introduces complexities, necessitating a reexamination of conventional team structures and the establishment of new collaborative norms in SE.

Promoting Ethical and Inclusive AI Development

Ethical deployment and inclusive practices were highlighted as fundamental. The symposium probed into AI's consequences on diversity, equity, and inclusion within SE and the larger societal matrix, emphasizing the imperative to develop AI systems that respect and champion these principles.

Adaptation to AI's Accelerated Progression

The symposium stressed the need for the SE community to stay agile in response to the swift progression of AI. Agility here is interpreted as the capacity for quick adaptation to technological shifts, as well as the openness to revamp processes, methodologies, and professional mindsets. A proactive stance in predicting and preparing for AI's future trajectories was advocated.

Human-Centric Values as AI Integration Foundation

The discussions reinforced the principle that AI integration should be rooted in human-centric values. AI is envisioned as an augmentative force, designed to bolster human expertise, creativity, and ethical discernment, not to render them obsolete.

15 S N O S U C N C

The symposium synthesized a vision of SE's future in the age of AI that balances technological progress with ethical and humanistic principles.

The outlined necessity for a well-considered, ethically informed, and educationally supported approach to AI integration informs the direction of SE. As the discipline progresses under AI's influence, these insights are instrumental in navigating the complexities and exploiting the transformative power of AI, with a steadfast commitment to human-centric engineering values.

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Our vision for AI in software engineering extends beyond mere efficiency. We aspire to create a just and inclusive future, prioritizing the overall welfare of humanity.

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The Copenhagen Symposium

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